

BA'ZI OLIMPIADA MASALALARI YECHIMLARIDAN NAMUNALAR**Qurbonov Sherzod Rashitovich***Shahrisabz "Temurbeklar maktabi" harbiy-akademik litseyi
matematika fani o'qituvchisi*

Annotatsiya. Matematika fanida olimpiada masalalarini o'rganish va o'rgatish ko'pgina maktab o'quvchi va o'qituvchilari uchun og'riqli masala hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun ushbu maqolada ba'zi olimpiada masalalarining yechimlaridan namunalar keltiramiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Ayniyat, tenglik, sistema, tenglamalar sistemasi, o'rta qiymatlar, uchburchak yuzi, kosinuslar teoremasi, tengsizlik, ishora, yechim.

1. Tenglamalar sistemasini yeching.

$$\begin{cases} 2 + 6y = \frac{x}{y} - \sqrt{x - 2y} \\ \sqrt{x + \sqrt{x - 2y}} = x + 3y - 2 \end{cases}$$

Yechilishi. Sistemaning birinchi tenglamasida $z = \sqrt{x - 2y}$ deb, shakl almashtirish qilganimizdan keyin $6y^2 + yz - z^2 = 0$ ga kelamiz. Ravshanki, $y \neq 0$ va $x > 2y$, chunki $z > 0$ (agar $x = 2y$ bo'lsa, u holda $y = 0$ bo'lar edi).

Oxirgi tenglamadan $6\left(\frac{y}{z}\right)^2 + \frac{y}{z} - 1 = 0$ ni hosil qilamiz. Bundan $\frac{y}{z} = -\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{y}{z} = \frac{1}{3}$ larni hosil qilamiz.

1-hol. $\frac{y}{\sqrt{x-2y}} = -\frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow \sqrt{x-2y} = -2y \ (y < 0) \Rightarrow x = 4y^2 + 2y \quad x$

ning bu qiymatini sistemaning ikkinchi tenglamasiga qo'yib, soddalashtirishdan keyin $4y^2 + 7y - 2 = 0$ ni hosil qilamiz. Bundan ($y < 0$) $y = -2$ va $x = 12$ ni topamiz.

2-hol. $\frac{y}{\sqrt{x-2y}} = \frac{1}{3}$ ($y > 0$) tenglikda shakl almashtirishlar va

$t = \sqrt{9y^2 + 5y}$ belgilash natijasida $t^2 - t - 2 = 0$ tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz.

Bu tenglamaning musbat yechimi $t = 2$ bo'lgani uchun,

$9y^2 + 5y - 4 = 0$ tenglamaga kelinadi. Bundan $\left(\frac{8}{3}; \frac{4}{9}\right)$ javob olinadi.

Javob: $(12; -2)$ va $\left(\frac{8}{3}; \frac{4}{9}\right)$

2. Quyidagi tengsizlikni isbotlang: $1 + \frac{1}{2^3} + \frac{1}{3^3} + \dots + \frac{1}{n^3} < \frac{5}{4}$

Isbot. Tengsizlikni isbotlashda $n^3 - n = (n-1)n(n+1)$ va $\frac{1}{(n-1)n(n+1)} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{(n-1)n} - \frac{1}{n(n+1)} \right)$ lardan foydalanamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + \frac{1}{2^3} + \frac{1}{3^3} + \dots + \frac{1}{n^3} &< 1 + \frac{1}{2^3 - 2} + \frac{1}{3^3 - 3} + \dots + \frac{1}{n^3 - n} = \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4} + \dots + \frac{1}{(n-1) \cdot n \cdot (n+1)} = \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} - \frac{1}{2 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot 3} - \frac{1}{3 \cdot 4} + \dots + \frac{1}{(n-1)n} - \frac{1}{n(n+1)} \right) = \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{n(n+1)} \right) = \frac{5}{4} - \frac{1}{2n(n+1)} < \frac{5}{4} \end{aligned}$$

3. Tengsizlikni isbotlang: $n! \leq \left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)^n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$

Isbot.

$$\begin{aligned} n! &= \sqrt{(n!)^2} = \sqrt{(1 \cdot n)(2 \cdot (n-1))(3 \cdot (n-2)) \dots (n \cdot 1)} = \\ &= \sqrt{1 \cdot n} \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot (n-1)} \cdot \sqrt{3 \cdot (n-2)} \dots \sqrt{n \cdot 1} \leq \\ &\leq \frac{1+n}{2} \cdot \frac{2+n-1}{2} \cdot \dots \cdot \frac{n+1}{2} = \left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)^n \end{aligned}$$

4. Tengsizlikni isbotlang: $\frac{1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdots (2n-1)}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdots (2n)} < \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$

$$\text{Isbot. } A = \frac{1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdots (2n-1)}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdots (2n)} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{3}{4} \cdot \frac{5}{6} \cdots \frac{2n-1}{2n} <$$

$$< \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{4}{5} \cdot \frac{6}{7} \cdots \frac{2n}{2n+1} = \frac{1}{\frac{1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdots (2n-1) \cdot (2n+1)}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdots (2n)}} =$$

$$= \frac{1}{A(2n+1)} < \frac{1}{A \cdot 2n} < \frac{1}{A \cdot n} \Rightarrow A < \frac{1}{A \cdot n} \Rightarrow A^2 < \frac{1}{n} \Rightarrow A < \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}.$$

5. Agar $x \geq 0$, $x \in \mathbb{Z}$ uchun $x^3 + 7x^2 + 35x + 27$ ifodaning qiymati biror natural sonning kubiga teng bo'lsa, u holda shunday x larning barchasini toping.

Yechilishi. $x^3 + 7x^2 + 35x + 27 = a^3$ belgilash olamiz.

$(x+2)^3 < a^3 < (x+4)^3$ bo'lishini tekshirish qiyin emas. Shartga ko'ra x va a lar butun son bo'lganligidan $a^3 = (x+3)^3$ bo'lishi kelib chiqadi, ya'ni

$$x^3 + 7x^2 + 35x + 27 = (x+3)^3$$

Bu tenglamani yechish orqali $x = 0$, $x = 4$ sonlarni aniqlaymiz.

Javob: $x = 0$, $x = 4$

6. $a, b, c > 0$ shartda $abc(a+b+c) \leq a^4 + b^4 + c^4$

tengsizlikni isbotlang.

Isbot. O'rta arifmetik va o'rta geometrik qiymatlar orasidagi munosabatga ko'ra quyidagi tengsizliklarni yozishimiz mumkin:

$$a^4 + b^4 \geq 2a^2b^2$$

$$a^4 + c^4 \geq 2a^2c^2$$

$$c^4 + b^4 \geq 2c^2b^2$$

Bu tengsizliklarni qo'shib yuboramiz:

$$a^4 + b^4 + c^4 \geq a^2b^2 + a^2c^2 + c^2b^2 \quad (*)$$

Xuddi shu kabi

$$a^2b^2 + a^2c^2 \geq 2a^2bc$$

$$a^2b^2 + c^2b^2 \geq 2b^2ac$$

$$a^2c^2 + c^2b^2 \geq 2c^2ab$$

tengsizliklarni qo'shish orqali

$$a^2b^2 + a^2c^2 + c^2b^2 \geq a^2bc + b^2ac + c^2ab \quad (**)$$

(*) va (**) larga ko'ra $abc(a + b + c) \leq a^4 + b^4 + c^4$

ni hosil qilamiz.

7. $x^x + y^y = z^z$, $x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechilishi: Faraz qilamiz $m, n, p \in \mathbb{N}$ sonlar tenglamaning yechimi bo'lsin, ya'ni

$m^m + n^n = p^p$. U holda $p^p > m^m$, $p^p > n^n$ bo'ladi. Bundan,

$p > m$, $p > n$ kelib chiqadi. $p \geq m + 1$, $p \geq n + 1 \Rightarrow$

$$p^p \geq (m + 1)^{m+1} = (m + 1) \cdot (m + 1)^m \geq 2 \cdot (m + 1)^m > 2m^m$$

$$p^p > 2m^m$$

Xuddi shunday $p^p > 2n^n$ tengsizlikni hosil qilamiz. Oxirgi tengsizliklarni qo'shsak, $p^p > m^m + n^n$ ni olamiz. Bu esa farazimizga zid. Demak, tenglama yechimga ega emas.

$$8. \begin{cases} x^2 + xy + y^2 = a^2 \\ y^2 + yz + z^2 = b^2 \\ z^2 + zx + x^2 = c^2 \end{cases} \text{ (bunda } x, y, z, a, b, c \in \mathbb{R}^+) \text{ sistemadan foydalanib}$$

$xy + yz + zx$ yig'indini toping.

Yechilishi: Sistemani geometrik yo'l bilan yechamiz. Quyidagi chizmadan foydalanamiz:

Sistemadagi tengliklar kosinuslar teoremasiga ko'ra o'rinalidir.

$$S_{BOC} = S_1$$

$$S_{COA} = S_2$$

$$S_{BOA} = S_3$$

belgilashlarni kiritib,

$$S_1 + S_2 +$$

$$S_3 = \text{tenglikdan}$$

foydalanamiz:

$$S_1 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}xy, \quad S_2 =$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}yz, \quad S_3 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}xz$$

$$S = \sqrt{p(p-a)(p-b)(p-c)} =$$

$$= \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{(a+b+c)(b+c-a)(a+c-b)(a+b-c)}$$

Hosil qilingan ifodalarni yuqoridagi tenglikka qo'yib, misol shartida so'ralgan yig'indini topamiz:

$$xy + yz + zx = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \sqrt{(a+b+c)(b+c-a)(a+c-b)(a+b-c)}$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

- 1.Sh. Ismailov, A. Qo'chqorov, B. Abdurahmonov. Tengsizliklar-I. Isbotlashning klassik usullari / Toshkent, 2008 y.
2. Fizika, matematika va informatika jurnalining turli sonlari.